

SELF-ALIGN HYBRID TRICYCLE

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Abstract— The SELF-ALIGN HYBRID TRICYCLE is an innovative transportation solution designed to enhance stability, efficiency, and user experience in urban environments. Integrating self-aligning technology with hybrid power systems, this tricycle automatically adjusts its alignment to maintain optimal balance and safety, even on uneven terrains. The hybrid propulsion combines pedal power with electric assistance, offering a sustainable and versatile mode of transport. This design prioritizes eco-friendliness, ease of use, and comfort, making it an ideal choice for commuters seeking a reliable and energy-efficient alternative to traditional vehicles.

Keywords— Self-Align, Hybrid, Tricycle, Transportation, and Manufacturing, Design, etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

In our daily life it is necessary to reduce our work and save the time. Hence we require identifying the new ideas, which will help to achieve our goal. Vehicular pollution has grown at an alarming rate due to growing urbanization in India. The air pollution from vehicles in urban areas, particularly in big cities, has become a serious problem. The pollution from vehicles has begun to tell through symptoms like cough, headache, nausea, irritation of eyes, various bronchial and visibility problems. The main pollutants emitted from the automobiles are hydrocarbons, lead/benzene, carbon monoxide, sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide and particulate matter. The main cause of vehicular pollution is the rapidly growing number of vehicles.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

P.P. Dutta [1] He found that tricycle rickshaw is a very cheap means of short distance transportation both in city and in rural areas. Tricycle rickshaw is generally propelled by human energy. A study has been performed with the existing model and design of tricycle rickshaws. An effort has been directed to design a lightweight, high strength, and ergonomic both human pulled and electric powered hybrid rickshaws.

Gomish Chawla [2] His principle objective of research is to conceive, design, build and compete with a small electric as well as human powered tricycle. It should have a seating capacity of 2 riders in front and back position. The vehicle follows a tadpole structure; the design of which has been derived from passenger two rider bicycles.

Swarnim Shrishti[3] He found that running out of fossil fuels, harvesting human kinetic energy will provide an immediate solution to various mechanical challenges and fuel limitations. This project deals with developing a Human Powered Hybrid Vehicle that uses both human and solar energy to drive the vehicle. The main aim here is to fabricate a cost effective, easy to use and easy maintenance cum repairable vehicle with green personal mobility solution.

Mr. Atul Anant Deshpande [4] He found that at present many exciting development in electric vehicle technology are taking place. This project is focused on electrical powered tricycle which is categorized under Low Speed Vehicles (LVs) are an environmentally friendly mode of transport for short trips. The objective of the project is to design and develop a concept battery powered tricycle for multipurpose use and to choose the best concept to reduce the mass expensive batteries required.

III. MATERIAL SELECTION

Table-1 Properties of Materials

Material	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)
AISI 4130	205	435	7850
AISI 1018	200	370	7870
AISI 1022	140	205	7858

1) AISI 4130: AISI 4130 is a chromium molybdenum alloy steel specification. With a lower carbon content range AISI 4130 provides better weldability.

Table-2 Specification of AISI 4130

Element	Composition (%)
Carbon	0.28-0.33
Chromium	0.90-1.10
Manganese	0.40-0.60
Molybdenum	0.15-0.25
Silicon	0.10-0.35
Phosphorous	0.035 max
Nickel	0.25 max
Sulphur	0.040 max

2) AISI 1018:

AISI 1018 steel has excellent weldability. AISI 1018 steel offers a good balance of toughness, strength and ductility. Provided with higher mechanical properties, AISI 1018 includes improved machining characteristics. Specific manufacturing controls are used for surface preparation, chemical composition, rolling and heating processes. All these processes develop a supreme quality product that are suited to fabrication processes such as welding, forging, drilling, machining, cold drawing and heat treating.

Table-3 CHEMICAL PROPERTY

Element	Content (%)
Carbon	0.14 - 0.20
Iron	98.81 - 99.26
Manganese	0.60 - 0.90
Phosphorous	≤ 0.040

3) AISI 1022:

1022 is a general purpose low tensile carbon steel with a typical ultimate tensile strength range 360 - 560 Mpa. Characterized by excellent weldability, good machinability with reasonable strength and good ductility. 1022 is used by all industry sectors for applications involving welding or when high strength is not necessary.

IV. CAD MODEL & CAE

Figure-1 Driver Ergonomics

Figure-2 Frame
Table-4 Result Plot of Post Processing

RESULTS OF CHASSIS WITH THICKNESS 3.2 MM PIPES

Table-5 Result for 3.2 mm Pipe

Impact Type	Stress Value (MPa)	Displacement (mm)	Factor of Safety (FOS)
Front impact	107.63	14.22	1.9
Rear impact	34.949	0.319	5.8
Side impact	42.096	0.245	4.86

Similarly we calculated the Stress Value, Displacement & Factor of Safety for 1.2 mm, 1.6 mm & 3.2 mm Pipes. The results obtained is as shown Bellow.

Table-6 Results for pipes having different thickness

Pipe Thickness (mm)	Weight of Frame (kg)	Front Impact FOS	Rear Impact FOS	Side Impact FOS	Remark
1.2	10.76	1.1	3.58	2.62	Selected for frame
3.2	26.03	1.9	5.8	4.86	-
1.6	13.81	1.697	6.188	7.05	-

So on the basis of results obtained we selected the material AISI 1022 with OD 25.4 mm and 1.2 mm thickness.

V. Result

1) Battery (Mileage) calculations:

BATTERY SPECIFICATIONS:

VOLTAGE: 48 V

RATING: 36Ah

Discharge Time = T= Battery Rating / Current= 35/20

T= 1.75 Hr.

Distance = speed × time

= 30 × 1.75

= 53 Km

Table-7 Calculations for Charges

Particulars	Amount (Rs)
Fixed Charges (FC)	60
Energy Charges (EC)	153
Electricity Duty (ED)	45.5
Wheeling Charges	61.71
Fuel Adjustment Charges	9.69
Tax on Sale (TOS)	0
Total Estimated Bill	329.9

Mileage = 330/(30*51) = 0.22 Rs/ Km

2) Self-aligning mechanism:

From trial it is clear that the mechanism is tilt up to 10mm, but the range of tilting the mechanism can be varied by adjustable stopper.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Actually day by day the use of vehicle having engines are increasing, due to which the pollution is increased because of the byproducts escaped from such vehicles. So controlling the pollution is very important. So adopting electrical vehicles is necessary nowadays. Now India has also taking the steps ahead to replace all the engine vehicles by electrical vehicles. So our project is one of the step towards that vision. Our project is environment friendly and can be commercialized. It is very compact and anyone can use this safely.

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